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**A NOVEL MATERIAL FOR AN ADAPTIVE AND STEALTH NAVAL
PLATFORM**

Final Progress Report (Technical)

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2. Technical Section

2.1 Technical Objectives

A sandwiched energy-attenuation panel comprising of a core layer of cellular material is developed and characterized to determine its applicability as a stealth material for the construction of future undersea naval platform. The core is made from functionally graded open cell polyurethane foam. By filling these interstitial pores with fluid at a higher temperature (i.e. lower viscosity) an engineered layer (EL) is developed. Within the frequency range of 250-1000 Hz, the material was found to have 25% higher acoustic transmission loss (TL) than that predicted by the acoustic mass law. The material is also found to develop stiffness quickly but temporarily at high strain rate during explosive loading environment. This can be defined as its adaptive nature under high strain rate.

In the proposed study, skin layers will be added to this EL panel to develop a Fluid Filled Composite (FFC) panel. Tests will be performed to characterize this panel under acoustic, explosive and thermal loading environment. Limited tests were done on samples exposed to fluid and air on either side to better simulate naval platform's field conditions.

2.2 Technical Approach

The core engineered layer has to be provided with necessary protection by skin layers on both faces in order that it can perform its intended role as a platform material. Some of the major characteristics can be determined through the following tasks/sub-tasks:

Task 1: Selection of Material for the skin layers: In order to decide an acceptable material, a Quality Function Deployment (QFD) is used. The justification for the scores given to the materials in the QFD is based on how well they meet the intended requirement as a possible naval platform material (Figure 5). Some of the major requirements are:

- i. Better bonding with core layer so that the core layer and the skin layers together act as integral element.
- ii. Stiff, thin, flexible with smooth outside finish and
- iii. Puncture and fire resistant.

More explanation on these requirements is given in section 3.1.5.

Sub-task 1.1: Mechanical Characterization: Once the materials for skin layers were ascertained, mechanical properties were evaluated using ASTM D 3039 and ASTM D 3518 specifications. Section 3.2 is devoted to describe this sub-task.

Sub-task 1.2: Fabrication of the Fluid Filled Composite (FFC) Panel: Test sample were prepared using core layer with protected skin layer on one side and on both sides. Different combinations of skins were tried to understand how the location of a particular skin affects the overall characteristics.

Task 2: Stealth and Shock characterization: In addition to characterizing the FFC for its acoustics and explosive behavior, limited tests were performed to understand how FFC will perform in a thermal environment. Following tests were performed:

Sub-task 2.1: Stealth Characteristics: Within the frequency range of 250-1000 Hz, the material was found to have 25% higher acoustic transmission loss (TL) than that predicted by the acoustic mass law. Tests were also performed at higher frequency range (1k - 10k Hz). Results are provided in section 3.5.6.

Sub-task 2.2: Shock Characteristics: This task involves a series of controlled impact tests in the Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar setup in the velocity range of 10 m/s to 20 m/s to determine how the sandwich panel gains stiffness with increasing strain rate.

Sub-task 2.3: Thermal Management: determining the adaptability of the material when exposed to high heat. The idea behind thermal management is that a material will “actively” cool itself if fluid is allowed to move within the solid structure.

2.3 Progress Statement Summary

A fluid filled (FF) “Engineered Layer” comprising a core layer of cellular foam plus skin/s is developed and characterized under acoustics. Sound transmission loss at low frequency (250 – 1000 Hz) and high frequency (1-10 kHz) were obtained. Limited tests were performed to determine its underwater characteristics. To characterize its explosive behavior, low impact tests were performed using Split Hopkinson Pressure bar. Thermal management of the material is investigated using a new and innovative method created with experimental analysis and scientific thought in mind.

A number of market available fabric materials were evaluated for their compatibility with the core layer. Figure 1 below demonstrates TL test results through one such FFC where skin layers are made from Kevlar 779 Correctional grade and Kevlar 3x2 Twill weave. 51% of the interstitial pores in the core layer were filled with fluid (water). As high as 132dB TL through the sample is noticed. Influence of fluid in the pores was found by comparing with test done on a sample with no fluid in the pores, is found to be around 36 dB, which is equivalent to a 5” building wall with 2”x 4” stud framing covered by 2 sheets of gypsum board on both sides. Underwater test result did not yield any improvement for the FF composite over dry ones.

Thermal management tests demonstrated that there is induced circulation due to convection within the material due to the heating source in one area of the material. The dry core layer tests show a large initial spike in temperature due to the presence of air in the interstitial pores which can quickly move through the material. Dry core layer released the heat after reaching the 180°F steady state mark while the other 2 fluid filled samples held the heat for a longer duration. This is again due to their larger thermal mass.

Under impact load, the aluminum sample reveals that as the strain rate or impact velocity is increased, modulus gets decreased. The behavior is opposite in the case of the developed fluid

filled composites, where the samples stiffened with the increase in the strain rate. Under high strain rate during an explosion, the material is also found to develop stiffness quickly but temporarily. This can be viewed as “**adaptive nature**” of the developed material.

Figure 1: TL through a FFC with Kevlar 779 and Kevlar 3x2 Twill weave

Figure 2 below shows the fall specific stiffness (i.e. young’s modulus divided by mass density) versus strain rate for Aluminum and the FFC.

Figure 2: Specific Stiffness with Strain Rate

The FF composite developed is found to possess reasonable stealth and adaptive characteristics. It is also found to have proper thermal management capability. Thus, FF composite can be a good candidate material for future naval platforms.

3. Progress

This part of the report will be provided in the order that the tasks and sub-tasks are given in Technical Approach (section 2.2).

3.1 Selection of Material for the skin layers

The initial review of materials ranges from flexible and non-flexible body armor, various types of security screens, spray on blast coatings, to many different types of fabrics. Some fabrics worth noting are Kevlar, fiberglass, carbon fiber, ballistic nylon, and Nomex which were included in the QFD table.

The skin must be protective enough to prevent punctures, yet flexible enough to be used in varying shapes other than a simple flat panel. The samples tested for acoustic transmission loss and in other tests have configurations as follows:

1. Flat, dry face skin layer only

2. Flat, dry panel (two face layers and core polyurethane foam)

3. 1-way curved cylindrical dry panel

- 4. Flat, fluid filled panel (two face layers and inner polyurethane foam filled with fluid)

3.1.1 Body Armor

Initial review started with evaluating body armor and conventional types of armor. There are many types of soft (flexible) and hard (non-flexible) body armors available in the market. The National Institute of Justice (NIJ) has standardized requirements for ballistic vests to be rated against [1]. The different protection levels represent the grades from lowest to highest protection, as shown in Figure 3. The soft body armor tends to use Kevlar, or a fabric similar to it, and could stop lower level ballistic threats. The soft body armor is flexible, but is usually only designed to stop lower level ballistic threats and can typically not stop a needle puncture unless specifically designed for this purpose.

Body Armor Threat Levels		NIJ STANDARD 0101.03	
		CALIBER	VELOCITY (fps)
LEVEL I		.22 LRHV (40g) Lead	1,050 – 1,100
		.38 Caliber (158g) Lead Round Nose	850 – 900
LEVEL IIA		.357 Magnum (158g) Jacketed Soft Point	1,250 – 1,300
		9mm (124g) Full Metal Jacket	1,090 – 1,140
LEVEL II		.357 Magnum (158g) Jacketed Soft Point	1,395 – 1,445
		9mm (124g) Full Metal Jacket	1,175 – 1,225
LEVEL IIA		.44 Magnum (240g) Lead Semi Wadcutter	1,400 – 1,450
		9mm (124g) Full Metal Jacket	1,400 – 1,450
LEVEL III		7.62 mm (150g) (.308 Caliber) Full Metal Jacket	2,750 – 2,800
LEVEL IV		30.06 (166g) (.30 Caliber) M2AP Armor Piercing	2,850 – 2,900

Figure 3: NIJ Body Armor Threat Levels

The higher levels of threat protection tend to use ceramic plates of differing composition to stop a high power round and they are called hard body armor. Although some companies claim to not use ceramic plates, they are still not flexible and are unwieldy for this project’s purposes. The only way manufacturers get flexibility in their hard body armor is by creating a different

arrangement of smaller ceramic plates to achieve flexibility in specific areas. These tend to have a high weight and high cost because they are manufactured for the single purpose of protecting a human and not made for alternate functions.

3.1.2 Security Films/Laminates

Security films are clear sheets of polyester that adhere to windows to protect them from many different types of threats. They are abrasion resistant and can be used from vehicle windshields to windows in office buildings. Their basic requirement is to stop an impact from shattering the glass so they are very good at holding a structure together. The fact that these are made strictly for windows makes them hard to affix to anything else that could possibly have a rougher surface finish. Attaching them to something they are not designed for can also have negative consequences on their described abilities.

3.1.3 Blast Coating

A blast coating from Defenstech is a spray on layer of polyurea and urethane-polyurea in a two-part system called Defend-X® with the material properties shown in Figure 4. Treated surface cures to a rubber like and flexible surface. The company claims to gain 100% structural integrity of the material it is bonded to with only a 1/8” thick layer [2]. This layer is constructed to stop shards from penetrating and splintering the material. The flexibility of the layer is good and can be bonded to many different types of materials. The negative aspects of this product are that the availability is very limited, (only offered by Defenstech) which therefore makes the cost very high. This cannot be made in-house either, as the Defenstech technicians must spray this into sheets and then ship the layers.

MATERIAL PROPERTIES			
PROPERTY	ASTM METHOD	TYPE I	TYPE II
Density, pcf (pcm)	ASTM D-1622	70 (2)	70 (2)
Hardness (shore D)	ASTM D-2240	40-46	42-50
Tensile Strength, psi (MPa)	ASTM D-412	4,000 (27.5)	2,300 (15.8)
Elongation (%)	ASTM D-412	700 (+/-90)	150
Young's Modulus, psi (MPa)	ASTM D-412	13,000 (89.6)	25,000 (172.3)
Tear Resistance, psi (MPa)	ASTM D-1004	370 (2.5)	400 (2.7)
Color		Gray	Gray

Figure 4: Material Properties of Defend-X® [2]

3.1.4 Fabrics

Certain types of ballistic and military grade fabrics provide a viable option for skin layer as expected in this project. Fabrics that were thoroughly researched are carbon fiber, Kevlar,

Nomex, fiberglass, and ballistic nylon. These fabrics are lightweight, tough, flexible, and are able to adapt to many different types of structures. Since a fabric is flexible in its unaltered state, it can be shaped into very intricate or typically hard to manufacture parts with fewer complicated steps. The fabrics can be impregnated with an epoxy matrix to stiffen them or left alone to achieve high flexibility. Each type of fabric is suitable for certain unique application. Carbon fiber has high stiffness whereas Nomex performs best in an environment with extreme high heat. Fiberglass is lightweight and also much more economical than most others but certainly not as strong. Ballistic nylon is a very tough, abrasion resistant fabric that was first developed as flak jackets during World War II and is now commonly used in applications that need abrasive protection at a relatively low cost such as in luggage. A stronger more adaptable fabric called Kevlar has replaced ballistic nylon in applications where penetration threats are more severe.

Kevlar, manufactured by DuPont, combines many of the properties that are featured in the other fabrics into an all around fabric that can be very adaptable to many situations. Kevlar is used in everything from bulletproof vests, puncture resistant vests, needle resistant gloves, helmets, and kayaks. There are different grades of Kevlar such as Kevlar 29, 49, and 149 with the greater number indicating a higher tensile modulus, but a lower tensile elongation. The fabric is very strong for its weight with a high modulus and high flexibility. It is also fire resistant and will not combust, but only degrade, at high temperatures (800° to 900°F). A table of properties of Kevlar is shown in Figure 5.

Its high strength and the capability of being manufactured in tight weaves, it is an excellent fabric for stopping stab and puncture threats, which is why it is used in many military and law enforcement applications. Kevlar's cut protection is shown in Figure 6, which is being compared to the cut protection of cotton and leather.

TABLE II-1. Typical Properties of Du Pont KEVLAR® 29 and 49 yarns

Property	Unit	KEVLAR 29	KEVLAR 49	Property	Unit	KEVLAR 29	KEVLAR 49
YARN				THERMAL PROPERTIES			
Type	denier (dtex) # of filaments*	1,500 (1,670) 1,000	1,140 (1,270) 768	Shrinkage			
Density	lb/in. ³ (g/cm ³)	0.052 (1.44)	0.052 (1.44)	In Water at 212°F (100°C)	%	<0.1	<0.1
Moisture Levels				In Dry Air at 351°F (177°C)	%	<0.1	<0.1
As Shipped**	%	7.0	3.5	Shrinkage Tension			
Equilibrium from Bone-Dry Yarn***	%	4.5	3.5	In Dry Air at 351°F (177°C)	G/D (cN/tex)	<0.1 (0.88)	<0.2 (1.77)
TENSILE PROPERTIES				Specific Heat			
Straight Test on Conditioned Yarns [†]				At 77°F (25°C)	cal/g x °C (J/kg x K)	0.34 (1,420)	0.34 (1,420)
Breaking Strength	lb (N)	76.0 (338)	59.3 (264)	At 212°F (100°C)	cal/g x °C (J/kg x K)	0.48 (2,010)	0.48 (2,010)
Breaking Tenacity	g/d (cN/tex) psi (MPa)	23.0 (203) 424,000 (2,920)	23.6 (208) 435,000 (3,000)	At 356°F (180°C)	cal/g x °C (J/kg x K)	0.60 (2,515)	0.60 (2,515)
Tensile Modulus	g/d (cN/tex) psi (MPa)	555 (4,900) 10.2 x 10 ⁶ (70,500)	885 (7,810) 16.3 x 10 ⁶ (112,400)	Thermal Conductivity,			
Elongation at Break	%	3.6	2.4	BTU x in./h x ft ² x °F [W/(m x K)]		0.3 [0.04]	0.3 [0.04]
Resin Impregnated Strands ^{††}				Decomposition			
Tensile Strength	psi (MPa)	525,000 (3,600)	525,000 (3,600)	Temperature in Air ^{†††}	°F (°C)	800-900 (427-482)	800-900 (427-482)
Tensile Modulus	psi (MPa)	12.0 x 10 ⁶ (83,000)	18.0 x 10 ⁶ (124,000)	Recommended max.			
				Temperature Range for Long-Term Use in Air			
				°F (°C)			
				300-350 (149-177)			
				300-350 (149-177)			
				Heat of Combustion			
				BTU/lb (Joule/kg)			
				15,000 (35 x 10 ⁶)			
				15,000 (35 x 10 ⁶)			
				Poisson's Ratio			
				0.36			

NOTE: The data in this table are those most commonly observed and are representative of the particular denier and type indicated; they are not product specifications. Properties will vary with denier and type. For KEVLAR 29, the basis weight used to calculate denier is zero finish and 4.5% moisture. For KEVLAR 49, the basis weight used to calculate denier is zero finish and 0% moisture. *Filament diameter is 0.00047 inches (12 microns). **Typical moisture levels on yarn as shipped; they reflect values reached at normal, moderate temperature and humidity levels following fiber production, which is a wet process.

***Equilibrium values are determined by bone drying the fiber and conditioning at 75°F (24°C), 55% RH.

[†]ASTM D885-85, tested at 1.1 twist multiplier.

^{††}Epoxy-impregnated strands, ASTM D2343.

^{†††}Varies with rate of heating.

Figure 5: Properties of Kevlar from DuPont's website KEVLAR® A RAMM FIBER II-1

3.1.5 Decision

In order to screen the materials to explore further, a Quality Function Deployment (QFD) has been used. The requirements of the project are given a number ranging from 1-5 with a higher number indicating a higher priority. Each type of material is then graded, 1, 3, or 9 with how well this specific material meets the requirement. The individual grade is multiplied by the priority, and the values summed to give a final score. On the basis of the QFD chart, Kevlar is selected for all subsequent tests. This QFD also justifies that further research should consider fabric, and that Kevlar is the best fabric for the testing. Kevlar is better than carbon fiber due to its reduced cost and higher shear resistance.

Figure 6: Cut Protection of Kevlar from DuPont’s website

Many of the scores given to the materials in the QFD are subjective nature and are based on their application potential. The following list is the justification for the scores given to each of the materials because of how well they meet the requirements.

- Bonding with the core layer can be done in many different ways for the several different proposed materials. The entire skin layer materials received the highest possible score of 9 because they all can bond well to polyurethane foam. The only difference is the type of method or material used to bond them together.

QFD - Material Selection for Skin Layer									
Requirements	Priority	Ceramic Armor	Blast Spray	Security Screen	Carbon Fiber	Kevlar	Nomex	Fiberglass	Ballistic Nylon
Bonding with Core Layer	4	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9
Thickness/weight	4	3	9	3	9	9	9	3	3
Flexibility	5	1	9	9	9	9	9	9	9
Puncture Resistance	4	9	9	1	3	9	1	1	1
Smooth Surface Finish	4	9	3	9	3	3	3	3	3
Fire Resistance	4	9	9	1	9	9	9	9	3
Acoustic Dampening	2	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	1
Cost	5	1	1	3	9	9	9	9	9
Availability (purchase)	3	3	1	9	9	9	9	9	9
Score		177	215	181	251	275	243	219	195

Figure 7: A Quality Function Deployment of the various materials being considered

- The thickness and weight of the skin layer will differ depending on the amount of protection needed but the minimum thickness and weight have been taken into account. Ceramic armor has been given a low score due to its high weight and thickness compared to the other materials. A moderate score of 3 has been given to the fiberglass and ballistic nylon because of the amount of layers that would be needed to offer the same

type of protection as the other strong fabrics or blast spray. The security screen has been given a 9 because they are extremely thin and light relative to the amount of protection they offer.

- The flexibility is much simpler to define than many other requirements. The ceramic armor plates themselves have no flexibility, while all the other skin layers proposed here have much flexibility to a degree depending on the implementation of them.
- Puncture resistance gives high scores to the ceramic armor, blast spray, and Kevlar. These materials are all used for this purpose thus score highly in this category. The carbon fiber is a very strong material, but is somewhat weak in impact resistance therefore it receives a 3. The other four materials are not strong enough to rate with carbon fiber therefore they receive a lower score.
- A smooth surface finish can be achieved in any of the materials listed which is why none received the lowest score of 1. Ceramic and security screen are generally available in with smooth surface finish. Other materials do not need much effort to get them to become smooth either, but they do not come perfectly smooth from the factory.
- Fire resistance of a material can be tentatively determined on the basis of melting / decomposition temperatures. Some values are listed below in Figure 8 which is downloaded from the technical guide for Kevlar by DuPont. Ceramics are naturally heat resistant materials and therefore are rated highly in the analysis.
- Many of the materials offer little to no acoustic damping characteristics; therefore most of them were assigned a score of 1. The blast spray receives a score of 3 because it is urethane based foam, which is shown to dampen sound.
- The cost of the materials can vary greatly. The ceramic armor and blast spray have high initial cost due to their complex manufacture process. The ceramic armor can range in cost from \$150 to \$600 and up for a small 1ft x1ft piece. Both the ceramic armor and blast spray will cost more because they need to be custom manufactured. The security screen is not as expensive as the ceramic or blast spray. However, these must be installed by a professional. The fabrics are not as expensive, ranging from about \$15/yard for fiber glass to \$65/yard for carbon fiber. These fabrics do have an initial cost associated with them such as epoxies and tools to lay them in a matrix, but an entire set- up may cost about \$100 dollars.
- The availability of these materials gives an edge to all of the fabrics and the security screens. These products have multiple manufactures (excluding Kevlar and Nomex, manufactured by DuPont). DuPont has offered a great availability of Kevlar and Nomex. There are other aramid fabrics just like Kevlar and other fire resistant fabrics such as Nomex from different manufacturers. The ceramic armor is not as common, however they can be found in good quantity compared to blast spray. The blast spray is only offered by one company and thus a low score assigned on the issue of availability.

"Customary" (inch-pound) Units								
	Specific Density lb/in. ³	Tenacity 10 ³ psi	Modulus 10 ⁶ psi	Break Elongation %	Specific Tensile Strength*	CTE** 10 ⁻⁶ /°F	Decomposition Temperature °F (°C)	
KEVLAR 29	0.052	424	10.2	3.6	8.15	-2.2	800-900	(427-482)
KEVLAR 49	0.052	435	16.3	2.4	8.37	-2.7	800-900	(427-482)
Other Yarns								
S-Glass	0.090	665	12.4	5.4	7.40	+1.7	1,562 [†]	(850)
E-Glass	0.092	500	10.5	4.8	5.43	+1.6	1,346 [†]	(730)
Steel Wire	0.280	285	29	2.0	1.0	+3.7	2,732 [†]	(1,500)
Nylon-66	0.042	143	0.8	18.3	3.40	—	490 [†]	(254)
Polyester	0.050	168	2.0	14.5	3.36	—	493 [†]	(256)
HS Polyethylene	0.035	375	17	3.5	10.7	—	300 [†]	(149)
High-Tenacity Carbon	0.065	450	32	1.4	6.93	-0.1	6,332	(3,500)

*Specific tensile strength is obtained by dividing the tenacity by the density.
**CTE is the coefficient of thermal expansion (in the longitudinal direction).
[†]Melt temperature.

Figure 8: Comparison of properties of Kevlar to other fabrics from DuPont's website

3.2 Mechanical Characterization

Composite structures have been widely used for many years. Due to the extreme variability intrinsic in the production of composite materials, there is no well established exact data regarding the materials properties of composites. In order to more fully understand the physical response of this new material, it is necessary to characterize the outer composite skin layers by obtaining the values of fundamental materials constants such as the elastic modulus, Poisson's ratio and the shear modulus.

The properties of the skin layers will be evaluated using the specifications on tensile testing methods outlined in ASTM D 3039 (Standard Test Method for Tensile Properties of Polymer Matrix Composite Materials) and ASTM D 3518 (Standard Test Method for In-Plane Shear response of Polymer Matrix Composite Materials by Tensile Test of a $\pm 45^\circ$ Laminate).

3.2.1 Materials Tested

The specimens which have been developed for this project consist of woven textile fibers in an epoxy matrix. All specimens are fabricated using two dimensional plain woven or twill fiber mats. Three Kevlar / Aramid weaves and one carbon fiber weave (Figure 9) have been used with MAS Low Viscosity Epoxy Resin and Non-Blushing Slow Epoxy Hardener to create the outer layers. The specifications for these fibers can be seen below in Table 1, and examples of the fabrics can be seen in Figure 9.

Table 1 – Physical Properties of Fabrics

Material	Weight	Thickness
Kevlar 3x2 Twill Weave	9.0 OZ/YD	0.024”
Kevlar Plain Weave	5.0 OZ/YD	0.0100”
Kevlar 779 Correctional	3.90 OZ/YD	0.007”
Carbon Fiber 2x2 Twill Weave	5.8 OZ/YD	0.012”

(From left to right – 3x2 Kevlar Twill, Kevlar Plain, Kevlar 779 Correctional, Carbon Fiber 2x2 Twill)

Figure 9– Kevlar / Carbon Fiber Weaves

Test coupons were generated according to the guidelines outlined in ASTM D 3039 and later tested in an Instron MTS 858 Mini Bionix II tensile testing machine under quasi-static conditions. The results of these tests can be seen below, presented under the ASTM report guidelines.

3.2.2 Sample Preparation Process

Because of the anisotropic behavior of composite materials, several precautions were considered when testing these types of samples. Tension testing is performed to determine the modulus of elasticity, the stress strain curve, and the ultimate strength of the materials. This is usually accomplished by creating regular rectangular or ‘dog-bone’ test samples (Figure 10). Table 2 has the specifications on different dimensions of this coupon.

Composite laminas were prepared by impregnating the fiber mat material with the low viscosity epoxy. The epoxy was carefully spread across both surfaces of the fiber-mat to ensure complete saturation of the fibers with epoxy. The composites were then pressed between flat plates of aluminum pre-treated with Maguire’s Mirror Glaze maximum mold release wax. These plates were clamped and placed in a temperature-controlled oven at 55° C and allowed to cure for 12 hours.

Once the composite laminas were cured, test coupons were cut in the two primary fiber directions, as well as at 45°. ASTM guidelines specify that samples be obtained by die cutting, diamond sawing, or molding. In absence of these tools, several methods of obtaining samples were explored. The best results were obtained by cutting coupons traced onto the composite

sheets with razor edge scissors. Test specimen geometry used in current test is given in Figures 10 and 11, and conforms to the specifications given in ASTM D 3039.

Table 2: Specimen Geometry

Coupon Requirements	
Shape	Constant rectangular cross-section
Minimum Length	Gripping + 2 times width + gage length
Specimen Width	As needed
Specimen Width Tolerance	± 1 % of width
Specimen Thickness	As needed
Specimen Thickness Tolerance	± 4 % of thickness
Specimen Flatness	Flat with light finger pressure
Tab Requirements	
Tab Material	As needed
Fiber Orientation (composite tabs)	As needed
Tab Thickness	As needed
Tab Thickness Variation Between Tabs	± 1 % tab thickness
Tab Bevel Angle	5 to 90°, inclusive
Tab Step at Bevel to Specimen	Feathered without damaging specimen

Figure 10 – Geometry of Test Specimen (all dimensions are in inch)

Figure 11 – Geometry of Sample Coupon Stencil

Tabs were created by milling of aluminum strips to a 10° angle. These aluminum strips were then sheared to the appropriate size. The bonding areas of the tabs were sanded with 400 grit silicon carbide paper, and bonded to the samples using Loctite cyanoacrylate (superglue) adhesive. A photograph showing the geometry of the test samples can be seen below in Figure 12.

Figure 12– photograph showing the geometry of the test samples

3.2.3 Instrumentation

In the case of strain gage instrumentation, considerable experimental scatter can occur if the strain gage is not sufficiently large. This scatter can be minimized by selecting a strain gage which covers as many fibers as possible, in order to obtain the average strain within the sample. With this in mind, the Vishay 250UT was selected for our experiments. The 250UT is a 90° Tee rosette, which allows simultaneous measurement of both longitudinal and transverse strain (Figure 13). It has a gage length of 0.25 inches and is the largest strain gage available from Vishay with suitable geometry for our sample sizes. Composite materials are sensitive to thermal input, and a resistance of 350Ω was selected to minimize the thermal input from the strain gage itself.

Figure 13

Composite materials are especially prone to undesirable failure modes when gripped in uniaxial tests. In order to mitigate failure caused by stress concentration in the grips, aluminum tabs were used as defined by ASTM D 3039. Figure 14 shows a test specimen which has failed in an uninstrumented test. The failure can be observed near the grip in the upper right hand corner of the specimen area. This failure mode is within the test sample, which is an acceptable mode of failure in this type of testing.

Figure 14 – Preliminary Sample Test to Failure

Strain gage data was gathered using Vishay 250UT 350Ω Tee Rosette Strain Gages via a Vishay Model 2100 Strain Gage Conditioner and Amplifier System. Data was gathered using DaisyLab7 which sampled and recorded ASCII data points at a rate of 50Hz.

3.2.4 Calculation of the Material Characteristics

In order to interpret the voltages recorded by DaisyLab, the following calculations were made.

Voltage Ratio (V_r) is used to simplify the strain calculation. All variables are voltages, as measured by DaisyLab and recorded in the dataset.

$$V_r = \frac{V_{Strained} - V_{Unstrained}}{V_{Excitation}} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Uncorrected Strain ($\tilde{\epsilon}$) is given by the following equation, where G.F. is the gage factor of the strain gage, R_{lead} is the resistance of the lead wires attached to the strain gage and R_{gage} is the resistance of the strain gage (nominally 350Ω)

$$\tilde{\epsilon} = \frac{-4V_r}{G.F.(1 + 2V_r)} \left(1 + \frac{R_{lead}}{R_{Gage}}\right) \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

Shunt calibration was used to ensure validity of the measured strain. A precision 22.1 kΩ ±1% resistor was used before each test to simulate a compressive strain by shorting the leads of the strain gage with the known resistance. The simulated strain is given by the following equation.

$$\epsilon_s = \frac{-R_{gage}}{G.F.(R_{gage} + R_{resistor})} \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

The correction factor is then given by the ratio of the simulated strain to the indicated strain.

$$CF = \frac{\epsilon_s}{\tilde{\epsilon}} \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

Finally, the corrected strain is simply the correction factor multiplied by the indicated strain

$$\epsilon_{corrected} = CF \tilde{\epsilon} \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

Once corrected strain data was obtained, calculations were performed to obtain the stress present in the sample. Three measurements of width and sample thickness were taken immediately before each test, and the average area was used to calculate the stress

$$\sigma = \frac{P_{load}}{Area} \quad \text{Equation 6}$$

The following equation is used to obtain the tensile chord modulus of elasticity, where $\Delta\sigma$ is the difference in tensile stress as measured between 1000 and 3000 $\mu\epsilon$ and $\Delta\epsilon$ is the difference between the two strain points (nominally .002)

$$E_{chord} = \frac{\Delta\sigma}{\Delta\epsilon} \quad \text{Equation 7}$$

Poisson's ratio is similarly given, where $\Delta\epsilon_l$ is the difference in lateral strain between 1000 and 3000 $\mu\epsilon$ and the same in the axial direction ($\Delta\epsilon_l$) which is again nominally .002

$$\nu = \frac{-\Delta\epsilon_l}{\Delta\epsilon_l} \quad \text{Equation 8}$$

The shear modulus is given from the results of the specimens tested at $\pm 45^\circ$ to the primary ply directions. First the shear strain is calculated using the following equation where $\gamma_{1,2}$ is the shear strain and ϵ_x and ϵ_y are the normal strain in the longitudinal and lateral directions respectively.

$$\gamma_{1,2} = \epsilon_x - \epsilon_y \quad \text{Equation 9}$$

The shear modulus is calculated as the ratio of the shear stress to shear strain, where $\Delta\tau$ is the difference in applied shear stress between 2000 to 6000 $\mu\epsilon$ and $\Delta\gamma$ is the difference between the two shear strain points (nominally .004)

$$G_{1,2}^{chord} = \frac{\Delta\tau}{\Delta\gamma} \quad \text{Equation 10}$$

All samples were loaded using an MTS 858 Mini Bionix II using hydraulic grips and a constant head speed of .0656 in/min.

$$\text{Also, from reciprocal law: } V_{12} = V_{21} * (E_1/E_2) \quad \text{Equation 11}$$

3.2.4 Results

Material characteristics of the tested specimens are tabulated in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Material Characteristics

Material	E ₁ psi (GPa)	E ₂ psi (GPa)	V ₁₂	V ₂₁	G ₁₂ Psi (GPa)
Kevlar 3x2 Twill Weave (1-ply)	4842213 (33.385)	7377712 (50.867)	0.079	0.120626	356243 (2.4562)
Kevlar 3x2 Twill Weave (2-ply)	10212745 (70.413)	7754836 (53.467)	0.433	0.328872	708780 (4.8868)
Kevlar 2x2 Plain Weave (1-ply)	6604791 (45.538)	7061773 (48.688)	0.243	0.259412	359850 (2.481)
Kevlar 779 Correctional (1-ply)	1512327 (10.427)	6744015 (46.498)	0.055	0.24501	520622 (3.5895)
Carbon Fiber 2x2 Plain Weave (1-ply)	10131991 (69.857)	10197570 (70.309)	0.224	0.225771	792098 (5.4612)

Individual test results along with plots of the stress-strain curves and sample failure photographs appear in Appendix A.

3.3 Fabrication of the Fluid Filled Composite (FFC):

Sample preparation involves patent pending information that is not included here. It is possible to get a copy of this information after signing a non-disclosure agreement with New Mexico Tech.

3.4 Low Frequency (250-1000 Hz) Stealth characteristics

Stealth characteristics of the developed composite were determined through its attenuation or absorption of acoustic energy which can be calculated based on transmission loss values. Attenuation is defined as restriction of the passage of sound through the softer core. Soft porous materials absorb incident sound waves, converting them into heat. When fluid filled composites were exposed to acoustics, two mechanisms become responsible for the absorption of the acoustic energy:

- (1) Viscous-flow losses – when a structure with fluid-filled-interconnected –pores is under acoustics, there is relative motion between the fluid and the surrounding structure resulting in boundary-layer losses and
- (2) Internal Friction – under acoustics, porous structure will compress or flex, and loss of energy takes place by internal friction.

So, to achieve higher acoustic loss, it is necessary to provide a system that can undergo deformation. There should be some transport of one material over another. This transport will cause shear stress to develop. This shear in turn will give rise to heat and thus loss of energy. Individual contribution will depend on many parameters. Some of these parameters are: 1) characteristics of the porous structure, 2) characteristics of the fluid in the interstitial pores, and 3) Loading rate/ frequency/ intensity.

Sound transmission loss through a media is defined as the ratio between incident sound power (P_{in}) and transmitted sound power (P_{tr}) expressed in decibels.

$$TL = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{P_{in}}{P_{tr}} \right) \quad \text{Equation 12}$$

The transmission loss is also dependent on the incidence angle φ of the incident sound power, as defined in Figure 15. Additionally, the amount of transmission loss through a plate is greatly reduced when exposed to its coincidence frequency. The coincidence frequency is defined as

$$f_c = \frac{c^2}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{m}{D}} \quad \text{Equation 13}$$

where m is the surface mass and D is the plate bending stiffness as defined in Equation 14.

$$D = \frac{Et^3}{12(1-\nu^2)} \quad \text{Equation 14}$$

Figure 15 Definition of incident angle

Below the coincidence frequency, the mass law characterizes the transmission loss, since in this region the transmission loss is mostly dependent on the mass of the plate. Equation 15 gives the TL when incident wave impacts the sample at an angle φ .

$$TL(\varphi) \approx 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\omega m \cos \varphi}{2\rho c} \right) \quad \text{Equation 15}$$

Where ω is the fundamental frequency and ρ is the mass density of the material.

Above the coincidence frequency, the transmission loss is mainly determined by damping at the coincidence frequency and by the bending stiffness of the plate. However, in the current test, coincidence frequencies of the samples are much greater than the highest tested frequency.

3.4.1 Experimental Procedure

For these experiments, acoustic excitation consisting of white noise from 250 to 1000 Hz is produced with a loudspeaker. Microphone spectra were recorded with SigLab software, and the TL is calculated based on the following procedure. Figure 16 presents the concept used for TL computation [3]. Broadband sound waves generated by the loudspeaker propagate down the tube as a plane wave. Upon impinging on the sample face part of the wave is reflected back, part of it is absorbed by the sample, and part of it is transmitted through the sample. On each face of the sample, there is an incident and a reflected wave with amplitudes A and B , respectively.

Figure 16: Wave partition on the sample face.

Based on the scheme presented in Figure 16, one can write the following system of equations 16 in terms of wave amplitudes where α , β , γ , and δ , are parameters dependent on frequency ω .

$$\begin{Bmatrix} A_1(\omega) \\ B_1(\omega) \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \alpha(\omega) & \beta(\omega) \\ \gamma(\omega) & \delta(\omega) \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} A_2(\omega) \\ B_2(\omega) \end{Bmatrix} \quad \text{Equation 16}$$

Transmission Loss, TL [dB], is defined as: ten times the common logarithm of the ratio of the airborne sound power incident on the partition to the sound power transmitted by the partition and radiated on the other side. It is calculated as:

$$TL(\omega) = 20 \log_{10} |\alpha(\omega)| \quad \text{Equation 17}$$

The coefficient, $\alpha(\omega)$ in Equation 17 is calculated from the cross-spectra measurements taken with SigLab for the two termination boundary conditions.

Figure 17: Cross section of the impedance tube

3.4.2 Samples Tested

9 (nine) samples as given in Table 4 were made using different combination of skin layers made from both Kevlar/carbon fiber reinforced plastic laminas.

Table 4: Characteristics of the nine samples tested under acoustics

Sample No.	Fiber	Layers/ Laminas	Thickness of fiber mat (mm)	Fiber mat Weight (oz)	Weight (gm) of sample dry(wet)	Weight of fluid (gm)	% (Wt. of fluid/Total weight)
1	Kevlar 3x2 Twill	1 by 1	0.61	9	137	0	NA
2	Kevlar 3x2 Twill	1 by 1	0.61	9	119 (201)	82	41
3	Kevlar regular plane weave	1 by 1	0.25	5	123	0	NA
4	Kevlar correctional plane weave	1 by 1	0.18	3.9	115	0	NA
5	Kevlar 3x2 Twill	1 by 2	0.61	9	160	0	NA
6	Kevlar 3x2 Twill	1 by 2	0.61	9	139 (164)	24	15
7	Carbon 2x2	1 by 1	0.25	5.8	137	0	NA
8	Kevlar 3x2 Twill	2 by 2	0.61	9	176	0	NA
9	Kevlar 3x2 Twill	2 by 2	0.61	9	158 (201)	43	27

3.4.3 Transmission Loss Experimental Setup

Tests were conducted at the Air Force Research Laboratory located in Kirtland Air Force Base using an acoustic transmission loss testing tube. The tube consists of two lengths of PVC pipe that are clamped together after the sample is inserted into the holder. The PVC test tube was encased in concrete, which reflects any sound that escapes the tube back into the tube. A photograph of the testing tube before it was encased with concrete is shown in Figure 18. There are two microphones on both the incident and transmitted sound side of the pipe. A speaker produces a standing acoustic wave on the incident side that travels through the test sample. After passing through the sample, the two microphones on the transmitted side record the transmitted sound. On the transmitted side, the end of the pipe can either be open or closed. A series of different types of foam are inserted into the pipe and an aluminum plug is used to close the pipe. The different types of foam are necessary since just one type of material is not sufficient to absorb every frequency used during testing.

The panels were tested for frequencies between 250 and 1000 Hz [3]. For circular tubes, the upper frequency is dependent on the diameter. At frequencies above this range, the incident and reflected waves are not likely to be planar because of cross modes in the tube. The tubes were pressed to the walls of the panel through Plexiglas end covers. These covers were drawn tight by an aluminum hub surrounding the tube covers and the specimen. The aluminum hubs also served to reduce sound losses at the joint by providing a high impedance mismatch to the interior panel and surrounding atmosphere. A loudspeaker was used to generate a plane wave field in a standing wave tube and a single microphone was used to measure the transfer functions between the signal provided to the loudspeaker and the sound pressure at the four locations.

Figure 18: Acoustic Testing Tube

To test the samples, a program was used to create random noise throughout a specified frequency range and to record the outputs from all four microphones. After the test was completed, a Matlab program was used to convert the data into transmission loss through the sample. Figure 19 has the plots of transmission loss at different incident frequencies.

3.4.4 Testing Procedure

The testing procedure was the same for all of the samples and is detailed in the steps below:

1. The microphones were calibrated.
2. The sample was inserted into the holder. The holder was placed in the tester and the two halves were clamped together.
3. The program was run with the pipe either opened or closed.
4. The end condition of the pipe was changed and the samples were tested again.

3.4.5 Observations for Sandwich Plates

The plot of transmission loss versus frequency for all 9 samples is shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19(a): TL for sandwich panels

Figure 19 (b): Comparison with core only

3.5 High frequency (1-10 kHz) Stealth characteristics

3.5.1 Design of the Impedance Tube

3.5.1.1 ASTM Specifications

Section 3.4 demonstrates good stealth characteristics in the lower frequency range, between 250-1000 Hz. Naval applications also require characterization at higher frequency range, between 1-10 kHz. Naval applications will involve the usage of fluids, typically ocean water, as the medium through which acoustic sound waves will need to be passed. Variations in density, temperature, pressure and salinity will be critical concerns for such tests. ASTM C 384 – 90a is readily applicable to air as a medium for sound propagation but its validity for tests under fluidic conditions will have to be ascertained. This section will describe in detail the impedance tube design considerations, ASTM standard applicability and theoretical framework for tests with fluids as the medium and concerns as applicable to acoustics for naval requirements.

3.5.1.2 Theory

Acoustic property characterization involves three critical parameters, namely; transmission loss (TL) coefficient, absorption coefficient (α) and reflection coefficient. The primary concern in acoustic testing is the design of the acoustic impedance tube. The inner diameter of a cylindrical tube, and the length of the tube are two most important parameters. The thickness of the tube wall is also important as reflected waves must be absorbed by the wall. The *most important* criterion for design of an acoustic test apparatus is that the sound waves that are incident on the test specimens **must remain plane waves throughout the tube**. As stated by Lord et al [4] “a sound wave that propagates in such a way that the acoustic pressures, particle velocities, density changes, etc. each have **uniform** phases and amplitudes at all points in a given plane perpendicular to the direction of wave propagation is called a plane wave”. So long as the sound wave remains plane within the acoustic impedance tube, the equations 16 through 23 are applicable [4]. Equation 16 shows the pressure distribution along the span of the tube.

$$p(x, t) = A \sin \omega t + B \sin \left(\omega t - \frac{2\omega x}{c} - \theta \right) \quad \text{Equation 16}$$

where,

$p(x, t)$ = total acoustic pressure at a distance x

A = amplitude of incident sound wave

B = amplitude of reflected sound wave

ω = frequency of sound wave, rad/s

c = propagation of velocity of sound waves

$\frac{\omega x}{c}$ = phase angle correction due to the distance $2x$

θ = phase angle between the reflected and incident waves at the surface of the sample

The magnitude of the pressure wave is given by equation 17.

$$p|x, t| = A * A + B * B + 2AB \cos \left(\frac{2\omega x}{c} - \theta \right) \quad \text{Equation 17}$$

The location of maximum and minimum acoustic pressures occur where $\cos\left(\frac{2\omega x}{c} - \theta\right)$ has values equaling +/- 1. The maximum and minimum pressures are given by equations 18 and 19.

$$P_{\max} = |A + B| \quad \text{Equation 18}$$

$$P_{\min} = |A - B| \quad \text{Equation 19}$$

The intensities of incident and reflected waves are given by equations 20 and 21.

$$I_A = \frac{A^2}{2\rho c} \quad \text{Equation 20}$$

$$I_B = \frac{B^2}{2\rho c} \quad \text{Equation 21}$$

where,

ρc = characteristic acoustic impedance of the medium

So long as the acoustic energy does not escape from the tube, which is why the walls must be thick enough to absorb some of the reflected waves and not allow them to get transmitted through, the absorption coefficient is given by equation 22.

$$\alpha_n = \frac{4P_{\max}P_{\min}}{(P_{\max}^2 + P_{\min}^2)} \quad \text{Equation 22}$$

Sumali [5] defines the transmission loss coefficient as given in equation 23.

$$T_L = \frac{p_t}{p_i} \quad \text{Equation 23}$$

Where,

p_t = Transmitted pressure and p_i = Incident pressure

A schematic of the acoustic impedance tube, taken from ASTM C 384 – 90a is shown in Figure 20 [6].

Figure 20: Acoustic Impedance Tube Apparatus

3.5.1.3 Acoustic Tube Dimensions

Typically, ASTM C 384 – 90a is used for designing the diameter and length of the acoustic tube. The following equations 24 through 26 are used, under the condition that the sound waves are plane.

Diameter for circular cross section

$$d < 0.586\lambda \quad \text{Equation 24}$$

Diameter for rectangular cross section

$$d < 0.5\lambda \quad \text{Equation 25}$$

Length

$$L > \frac{3\lambda}{4} + d \quad \text{Equation 26}$$

where,

λ = Wavelength of forced vibration and is a function of the frequency and speed of sound in the medium denoted as c .

The **minimum wavelength** (λ_{\min}) is used from equations 24 and 25 and **maximum wavelength** (λ_{\max}) from equation 26.

3.5.1.4 Acoustic Tube Design

For **air as the media** within the tube, with $c = 343$ m/s, the calculated dimensions of the tube for the proposed frequency spectrum of 1 – 10 kHz are as shown in equations 27 through 30.

Diameter for circular cross section

$$d < 0.7913 \text{ in (2 cm)} \quad \text{Equation 27}$$

Diameter for rectangular cross section

$$d < 0.6752 \text{ in (1.715 cm)} \quad \text{Equation 28}$$

Length for circular cross section

$$L > 27.725 \text{ cm} \quad \text{Equation 29}$$

Length for rectangular cross section

$$L > 27.4401 \text{ cm} \quad \text{Equation 30}$$

For **sea-water as the media** within the tube, c or the speed of sound in water will vary as per the salinity, depth and temperature. Figure 21(a) and 21(b) show the variation of density and salinity with the depth of the ocean. Figure 22 shows the variation of speed of sound with density. Typically, sea-water density is taken as 1500 kg/m^3 . The specific acoustic impedance, defined as the product of the density and speed of sound in the particular medium (ρc) is $1.5 \times 10^5 \text{ g/cm}^2\text{s}$ for sea-water as referenced by Urick [7].

Figure 21: (a) Density variation with Ocean depth (b) Salinity variation with ocean depth

Figure 22: Speed of sound variation with ocean depth

3.5.1.5 Depth Range

The typical submarine dive operating depth is less than 1000 meters. However, deep diving submarines such as the Turtle and Alvin [8] have operating dive depths as deep as 2400 m and 6600 m. From, the Figure 22 above, it can be seen that the speed of sound will vary between 1460 kg/m³ to about 1600 kg/m³. Thus, the depth range is typically within 1000 meters but in some cases may be as high as 7000 meters. Usage of the same formulations from ASTM C 384 – 90a as listed previously in equations 24 through 26 and taking the density of sea-water as 1500 kg/m³, will result in the dimensions for the acoustic tube as shown in equations 31 through 34.

Diameter for circular cross section

$$\mathbf{d < 3.461 \text{ in (8.79 cm)}} \quad \text{Equation 31}$$

Diameter for rectangular cross section

$$\mathbf{d < 0.2953 \text{ in (7.5 cm)}} \quad \text{Equation 32}$$

Length for circular cross section

$$\mathbf{L > 121.29 \text{ cm} = 1.213 \text{ m}} \quad \text{Equation 33}$$

Length for rectangular cross section

$$\mathbf{L > 120\text{cm} = 1.2 \text{ m}} \quad \text{Equation 34}$$

3.5.1.6 Discussion on ASTM C 384 – 90a Applicability for Fluids

The most fundamental assumption in ASTM C 384 -90a is that the acoustic sound wave is plane in nature. The equations 24 through 26 are directly dependent on the diameter of the tube. This relation between the wavelength under consideration and the diameter of the tube is based off Lord Rayleigh's. Lord Rayleigh has stated that, "*in all cases, the waves ultimately become plane, if the forced vibration be graver than the gravest of the natural transverse vibrations.*"

However, the natural transverse vibration that Lord Rayleigh refers to is that of a cylindrical tube enclosing a *gas* and *not a fluid* such as sea water . If the medium within the acoustic tube is changed from a gas to a fluid, such as sea water, it will result in the direct addition of mass to the system but not stiffness. Thus, the natural frequency of vibration of a fluid-filled tube shall be different and expectedly lower than that of an air filled cylindrical tube. Thus, the relation given by equation 35, taken from Lord Rayleigh's book, may not be valid for the case of fluid filled cylindrical tubes. Note that r is the radius of the tube.

$$\lambda_{\max} = 3.413r \qquad \text{Equation 35}$$

Equation 24 and equation 35 are identical for the case of circular cross sections. The lowest mode for the transverse frequency is *expected to be lower* in the case of a fluid-filled tube in comparison to an air filled tube. Thus, the equations 24 through 26, and hence ASTM C 384 – 90a *may not be valid* for fluids. A mathematical relation for a fluid-filled hollow cylindrical tube dimensions and its *gravest transverse vibration* must be derived and compared with ASTM C 384 – 90a. The dimensions satisfying conditions for plane waves with air and sea-water as the media with a frequency range of 1 – 10 kHz must be then chosen as the design parameters for the acoustic impedance tube.

The lowest natural frequency is expected to be lower than that for an air filled tube, the inverse being larger than 3.413, the allowable diameter should be larger for a fluid filled tube. Thus, the limiting condition should be that for air as a medium and the lower diameter and larger length designed using ASTM C 384 – 90a should be acceptable even for a fluid filled tube to maintain the plane nature of the acoustic waves. Thus, the derivation is at this stage being by-passed. The tube dimensions have been designed based off ASTM C 384 – 90a as shown in equations 27 through 30.

Wall Thickness

The walls should be thick enough to prevent attenuation loss. Sumali [5] has used a wall thickness of 19.1 mm for the impedance tube design and reported a good correlation between theoretical and experimental prediction for higher frequencies. Hence, a wall thickness of 20 mm or 2 cm, the same as the inner diameter of the air-filled tube, is designed.

Material Non-homogeneity

It was stated above that the plane nature of the sound waves must be maintained in order for the formulations listed thus far to be valid. However, the sandwich composite being tested is itself non-homogeneous and anisotropic in nature. Thus, though the incident wave within an acoustic

impedance tube with air as the medium may remain plane for any range of frequencies so long as the dimensions are designed as per ASTM C 384 – 90a, the reflected wave need not be plane. Thus, the second term of equation 16, which represents the reflected portion of the wave, may not apply. Thus, the applicability of ASTM C 384 – 90a for tube designs with the specimens being non-homogeneous and anisotropic too is questionable. Thus, a theoretical framework including the directional variation of the material properties of the test specimens must be developed to ensure that the definition of plane waves is satisfied.

3.5.1.7 Construction of the Impedance Tube for Higher Frequency (HF)

In order to investigate the properties at frequencies, between 1-10 kHz, a standing wave tube which is capable of containing smaller wavelengths is constructed. The geometry of the new HF standing wave tube is based on ASTM C 384 – 90a, on the same principle as that of the setup at Air Force research laboratory, Kirtland, Albuquerque, NM. The instrumentation and experimental setup are based on the work of B. Song and J. S. Bolton [9], who developed an experimental transfer matrix method to estimate the characteristic impedance and wave number of homogeneous porous layers.

Description and calculation for the dimensions for the tube in the frequency range of 1-10 kHz with air as the transmission media are given in detail in the previous section. Thus, fabrication of the acoustic tube is based on circular cross section with diameter of the tube be less than 2cm, and the length be greater than 27.725cm. The following schematic diagram (figure 23), is a basic view of the testing setup incorporating an array of phase-matched microphones in each of the testing chambers.

Figure 23 – Schematic Diagram of Test Setup

3.5.2 Test Setup/ Instrumentation

3.5.2.1 Impedance Tube – PVC pipe with an inner diameter of .75 in (1.905 cm) and a length of 30 cm on each side of the sample. Additional length will be allowed for the anechoic termination – which can be replaced with a fully-reflective solid rod. The tube is surrounded in a concrete enclosure to ensure that all sound is absorbed by the test apparatus. Particle board was selected to form the enclosure within which the impedance tube will be enclosed.

3.5.2.2 Sound Source – A National instruments NI 9263 4-Channel, 100 kS/s, 16-bit, ± 10 V, Analog Output Module was used to generate the tones. This signal was amplified by a power amplifier in order to achieve appropriate loudness.

3.5.2.3 Speaker – A Kobitone 254-PS602-RO Mylar Speaker was used to project the sound. Due to the plane wave requirement, a speaker which fits entirely within the impedance tube is required. This speaker produces between 100-115 dB in the frequency range of interest, with a max distortion of 5% at 1600 Hz.

3.5.2.4 Microphone – G.R.A.S Type 40PH Array Microphones were used to record the complex pressures at specific locations within the impedance tube. These microphones have excellent sensitivity as well as a high dynamic range. These microphones also conform to IEEE-P1451.4, which allows TEDS connection directly to the data acquisition system.

Calculation of the characteristic impedance requires that no acoustic energy escapes from the medium. Based on the apparatus used at the AFRL, the new impedance tube will also be cast in concrete. The resulting stiffening raises the natural frequency of the tube and causes resonance in the frequency range of interest. In order to determine the natural frequencies of this tube, a finite element analysis is performed on the acoustic tube using SolidWorks COSMOSWorks. A Dimensioned drawing of the impedance tube, as well as the results of the frequency analysis are shown Figure 24.

Figure 24– Dimensions of Impedance Tube (cm)

3.5.3 Samples Tested

Six samples as given in Table 5 were prepared using different combination of skin layers made from two kinds of Kevlar fiber reinforced plastics. 12 tests were performed using 12 flat faces of these 6 samples.

Table 5: Characteristics of the six samples tested under this category

Sample No.	Faces	Layers/ Laminas	Foam only Weight (gm)	Weight (gm) of sample dry(wet)	Sample Weight with fluid (gm)	% (Wt. of fluid/Total weight)
1	Open/Kevlar	1	18.350	23.920	23.920	0
2	Kevlar 3x2 Twill on both faces	1 by 1	18.472	32.786	32.786	0
3	Kevlar 3x2 Twill / Kevlar correctional plane weave	1 by 1	18.213	26.493	26.493	0
4	Open/Kevlar	1	18.460	24.020	51.697	54
5	Kevlar 3x2 Twill on both faces	1 by 1	18.555	33.549	60.753	45
6	Kevlar 3x2 Twill / Kevlar correctional plane weave	1 by 1	18.183	25.352	52.169	51

3.5.4 Finite Element Analysis

Support conditions are so fixed to keep the natural frequency below the frequency range of interest. Thus, a finite element investigation was performed. The mesh was generated with p-type polyhedral elements, six degrees of freedom per node. The system was restrained along its bottom edge with roller type restraints (allowing translation along two axes), and against translation along one edge. Frequency analysis is not highly mesh dependent, and the automatically calculated mesh size for a stress analysis was used. The following table outlines the parameters set within SolidWorks for the analysis.

Mesh Information

Mesh Type:	Solid mesh
Mesher Used:	Standard (p-type)
Automatic Transition:	Off
Smooth Surface:	On
Jacobian Check:	4 Points
Element Size:	9.6677 mm
Tolerance:	0.48338 mm
Quality:	High
Number of elements:	32801
Number of nodes:	49197
Time to complete mesh(hh:mm:ss):	00:00:07
Computer name:	ME58

3.5.4.1 Materials Constants

The following tables present the materials constants used in the finite element analysis of the standing wave tube.

For concrete:

Property Name	Value	Units	Value Type
Elastic modulus	2.5e+010	N/m ²	Constant

Poisson's ratio	0.15	NA	Constant
Shear modulus	1.4e+010	N/m ²	Constant
Mass density	2300	kg/m ³	Constant
Tensile strength	1.7234e+008	N/m ²	Constant
Compressive strength	5.5149e+008	N/m ²	Constant
Thermal expansion coefficient	1e-005	/Kelvin	Constant
Thermal conductivity	1.4949	W/(m.K)	Constant
Specific heat	877.96	J/(kg.K)	Constant

For particle board

Property Name	Value	Units	Value Type
Elastic modulus	2.6e+009	N/m ²	Constant
Poisson's ratio	0.29	NA	Constant
Shear modulus	3.5e+008	N/m ²	Constant
Mass density	670	kg/m ³	Constant
Yield strength	1.38e+007	N/m ²	Constant
Thermal conductivity	0.05	W/(m.K)	Constant

For PVC 0.007 Plasticized tube

Property Name	Value	Units	Value Type
Elastic modulus	6e+006	N/m ²	Constant
Poisson's ratio	0.47	NA	Constant
Shear modulus	2e+006	N/m ²	Constant
Mass density	1290	kg/m ³	Constant
Tensile strength	1.3e+007	N/m ²	Constant
Thermal conductivity	0.16	W/(m.K)	Constant
Specific heat	1600	J/(kg.K)	Constant

For 6061 Alloy

Property Name	Value	Units	Value Type
Elastic modulus	6.9e+010	N/m ²	Constant
Poisson's ratio	0.33	NA	Constant
Shear modulus	2.6e+010	N/m ²	Constant
Mass density	2700	kg/m ³	Constant

Tensile strength	1.2408e+008	N/m ²	Constant
Yield strength	5.5149e+007	N/m ²	Constant
Thermal expansion coefficient	2.4e-005	/Kelvin	Constant
Thermal conductivity	170	W/(m.K)	Constant
Specific heat	1300	J/(kg.K)	Constant

3.5.4.2 Observations

The following table and images illustrate the fundamental frequencies of vibration for the new HF impedance tube. Most of the acoustic energy is absorbed in the first few modes of vibration, which are below the lower threshold of our intended frequency spectrum. The higher modes may contribute to errors, and the data will be carefully examined around those frequencies.

Mode	Frequency (Hz)
1	40.95
2	404.99
3	854.02
4	1091.2
5	1288.6
6	1525.3
7	1559.2

3.5.5. Higher frequency Test

Six panels were tested for frequencies between 1 kHz and 10 kHz. A loudspeaker was used to generate a plane wave field in a standing wave tube and a single microphone was used to measure the transfer functions between the signal provided to the loudspeaker and the sound pressure at the four locations.

3.5.6 Observations

All these tests have provided some more knowledge about this novel material developed. Test 1 – Acoustic Transmission Loss (TL) tests are performed at high frequency (1 – 10 kHz) range using the same test setup developed at New Mexico Tech (NMT) using the DAQ system based on Kirtland Air Force Research Laboratory (AFRL). Figures 25 to 30 below plot Transmission Loss of the six samples with 12 sides. Frequency is plotted in x-axis and dB is plotted in y-axis.

Mode Shapes are:

Figure 25: TL for the Sample 1 as given in Table 5

Figure 26: TL for the Sample 2 as given in Table 5

Figure 27: TL for the Sample 3 as given in Table 5

Figure 28: TL for the Sample 4 as given in Table 5

Figure 29: TL for the Sample 5 as given in Table 5

Figure 30: TL for the Sample 6 as given in Table 5

3.6 Underwater (UW) Stealth Characteristics

3.6.1 Design Specifications

UW acoustic tube must be capable of accurately measuring the acoustic properties of a material sample while submerged in water comparable to that of seawater. Design rationale for the UW test setup is provided in section 3.5.1.4. These specifications require that the length of the tubes be 50 and 52 in. for the incident and transmission parts respectively. The tubes must have an inner diameter less than 3.461 in. In order to maintain testing accuracy the sound wave hitting the sample must be a plane wave.

3.6.2 Material and Instrumentation Selection

3.6.2.1 Body

A 3 in. schedule 40 PVC pipe was chosen to construct the transmission and incident parts in order to maintain acoustic and corrosion resistant properties while in water. This tube is cased in cement and an outer casing made from 0.5 in. thick acrylic plating. In order to ensure that all sound waves reflecting off inner surfaces of the testing chamber are terminated, a 4 in. thick urethane anechoic foam padding is applied to the opening and end of the testing apparatus. This will increase the accuracy of results by maintaining a plane wave within the testing chamber. The sample mount was made from stainless steel to survive in the water environment.

Figure 31: Cross section of the UW impedance tube

3.6.2.2 Instrumentation

The most important design characteristics of an impedance tube is the generation of a plane wave. Due to the fact that the speaker is larger than the minimum diameter of the transmission tube the wave must be generated by cutting off an omni directional wave with an annulus. The wave that travels down the tube will be an approximate plane wave as long as all waves not traveling down the tube are terminated to avoid interference. This particular speaker setup requires that a length of at least 20 in. be between the speaker and annulus in order to ensure that the remaining wave is within 0.1% of a plane wave. Using this as the primary design specification along with the other geometric dimensions the impedance tube was initially drawn as shown in figure 31.

In order to accurately measure the magnitude of reflected and transmitted sound waves, Reson TC4013 miniature reference hydrophone was used. This hydrophone was selected by size (Φ 9.5mm), operating frequency range (1 Hz – 170 kHz), and sensitivity (-211 dB). The sound waves will be produced by the Lubell Labs UW30 underwater speaker.

Figure 32: The underwater test setup is on the test floor ready for the test

3.6.3 Test Performed

Two samples were tested using the configuration #1 of Table 5 of section 3.5.3. Tests were performed using both dry and fluid filled samples. Sample 1 corresponds to the dry sample and sample 2 corresponds to fluid filled. Each sample was tested in following two settings:

- When the incident tube air filled and the transmitted tube is water filled and
- When both the tubes are filled with water.

Again, both faces were exposed to the incident acoustics.

3.6.4 Observations

Transmission loss through the FFC is plotted in figures 33a and 33b.

Figure 33a: Underwater transmission loss for sample 1

Figure 33b: Underwater transmission loss for sample 2

3.6.5 Discussion

Under water high frequency acoustic transmission loss tests were performed using two samples. Figures 33(a,b) give the plots of the TL with frequency for the frequency range between 1 – 10 kHz. When compared with the plot in figure 25, it is clear that the TL is much higher when the medium is air. Influence of fluid is not appreciable.

3.7 Shock Characteristics

3.7.1 The Test

The focus of this part of the research was to develop improved multi-layer composite foam materials and perform subsequent laboratory test in order to quantify the ability of these materials to reduce the amount of impact energy which is transmitted through them. In particular, we seek to quantify the effect of fluid-filled pores on the impact and vibration transmission properties of the composite foams.

Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar (SHPB) system was utilized to investigate this response.

3.7.2 Impedance

At high impact velocity, even objects with low mass may generate a significant amount of impact energy, and the resulting transmission of the impact energy through the engineered component may adversely affect the performance and longevity of the component. It is desirable

to develop improved lightweight composite materials, which are able to attenuate impact energy transmission for a wide variety of applications.

The testing of polymer materials using a SHBP system can provide some challenges due to their low mechanical impedance. The mechanical impedance, represented as ‘Z’, is the product of the (area) x (density) x (longitudinal sound speed). In order to get optimum sensitivity from the instrument, it is desirable to match the impedance of the pressure bar material to that of the sample as closely as possible. Mechanical Impedance for selected metals and polymers are provided in Table 6.

Table 6: Impedance of various materials

Metals and Alloys	Impedance
304 Stainless Steel	36.08
Brass	31.48
Titanium	23.64
Beryllium	14.80
6061 Aluminum	14.40
AZ31B Magnesium	8.02

Polymers	Impedance
Neoprene	4.01
Teflon	3.96
Polyurethane	3.14
Nylon	2.93
Lucite	2.67

3.7.3 Impact velocity

Because the multi-layer polymer samples are very effective at attenuating the compressive strain-waves, which are produced by the initial impact, it can be difficult to get an adequate reading from the strain gage located on the output bar of the system. For this reason, it is desirable to use as high of an initial impact velocity as possible as it will provide a higher amplitude wave, which is easier to measure accurately. However, the maximum impact velocity that may be used is limited by the material properties of the pressure bars. In order to avoid damaging the bars, the impact pressure must be kept below the Yield Strength of the bar material. The impact pressure is determined by using the Rankine-Hugoniot Jump Equations, and is a function of the density, sound speed, and impact velocity. Table 7 lists the maximum allowable impact velocities when using Aluminum 6061 and Magnesium AZ31B alloy pressure bars, assuming a yield strength of 145 MPa and 97 MPa for the respective alloys. As shown, the Magnesium AZ31B alloy allows an increase of approximately 20% as compared to the Aluminum 6061 bars which were used previously.

Table 7: Maximum Impact Velocities Required to remain Below Bar Yield Point

Bar Material	Maximum Velocity (m/s)	Maximum Velocity (MPH)
6061 Aluminum	20.0	44.74
AZ31B Magnesium	24.1	53.91

Compressed air is used in the SHPB system to launch a projectile which in turn creates the initial impact. The velocity of the projectile is measured by using two infrared photodiodes, which are connected to a data acquisition system. The figure 34 below was constructed to verify that our system is capable of achieving the velocity listed in Table 3 for the AZ31B alloy.

Tank Pressure (PSIG)	Impactor Velocity (m/s)
0	0
5	10.8
10	16.1
15	19.8

Figure 34: Impact Velocity vs. Air Pressure using the New Mexico Tech SHPB System

3.7.4 Split Hopkinson Pressure bar (SHPB)

The SHPB will be utilized to determine the response and characteristics of the composite. The apparatus consists of a gas gun with an impactor bar, an input and an output bar. Figures 35 and 36 below illustrate the setup of the apparatus. The impactor sends a shockwave through the input bar, the sample under investigation, and the output bar. The strain caused by the shockwave is measured in the input and output bar by strain gauges and these values are used to determine the strain and other properties of the material under investigation. According to Kaiser [10], the

SHPB can be summarized as follows:

1. the reflected and transmitted waves are proportional to the specimen's strain rate and stress respectively.
2. by integrating over time the strain rate history generated from the test, the strain in the sample can be determined and,
3. stress-strain properties can be calculated by analyzing the strain in the input and output bars. The shockwave produced takes the shape as shown in Figure 37.

Figure 35: The SHPB setup in the Laboratory

Figure 36: Schematic of the sample-bar interface and sample

The impactor strikes the input bar (incident bar) and creates a pulse that is measured by the strain gauge on the incident bar; a reflected pulse is then reflected from the input bar and sample interface and measured by the strain gauge in the incident bar. Thus, the strain gauge on the incident bar measures both the incident pulse $\epsilon_i(t)$ and reflected pulse $\epsilon_r(t)$. According to Ninan et.al [11], the displacement of the incident bar-sample interface $u_I(t)$ is determined by $\epsilon_i(t)$ and $\epsilon_r(t)$ as,

$$\epsilon_i(t) = \epsilon_I(t - \Delta t) \quad \text{Equation 36}$$

$$\epsilon_r(t) = \epsilon_I(t + \Delta t) \quad \text{Equation 37}$$

Where Δt is the time for the pulse to travel from the strain gauge on the input bar to the sample, and t is an instant in time. Displacement in the input bar and the sample interface is given by equation 38 and equation 39 gives the displacement at the sample and output bar interface.

$$u_1 = C_0 \int_0^t (-\varepsilon_i + \varepsilon_r) dt \quad \text{Equation 38}$$

$$u_2 = -C_0 \int_0^t \varepsilon_t dt \quad \text{Equation 39}$$

The average strain in the sample is:

$$\varepsilon_s = \frac{u_2 - u_1}{l_0} = \frac{C_0}{l_0} \int_0^t (-\varepsilon_t + \varepsilon_i - \varepsilon_r) dt \quad \text{Equation 40}$$

Where l_0 is the sample length and C_0 is the longitudinal wave velocity in the bar. Loads at the sample interfaces P_1 and P_2 can be determined from the following equations:

$$P_1 = A_s E (\varepsilon_i + \varepsilon_r) \quad \text{Equation 41}$$

$$P_2 = A_s E \varepsilon_t \quad \text{Equation 42}$$

Assuming that the pressure difference at each interface of the sample is negligibly small then according to Graff [12], $\varepsilon_t = \varepsilon_i + \varepsilon_r$ and substituting this into equation 40 gives:

$$\varepsilon_s(t) = - \frac{2C_0}{l_0} \int_0^t \varepsilon_r dt \quad \text{Equation 43}$$

which represents the sample average strain.

The stress is obtained directly from the transmitted strain, and the strain rate in the specimen and are given by

$$\sigma_s = E \frac{A_0}{A_s} \varepsilon_t \quad \text{Equation 44}$$

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_s = \frac{-2C_0}{l_0} \varepsilon_r \quad \text{Equation 45}$$

- C_0 is the wave propagation velocity
- l_0 is the specimen length
- E is Young's Modulus of output bar
- A_0 is the cross sectional area of output bar
- A_s is the cross section of the specimen
- ρ is the density of the material
- ε_t is the strain in the output bar
- ε_r is the strain in the input bar

Split Hopkinson pressure bar equations given above can also be applied to composites. According to Ninan et.al [11], there has been few but relatively recent attempts, to systematically model the rate-dependent deformation of composite laminates beyond the elastic region.

Cited from: <http://www.tut.fi/index.cfm?MainSel=12870&Sel=13652&Show=18694&Siteid=142>
 Figure 37: Example of the incident, reflected and transmitted pulse.

When the incident bar is struck by the impactor, an elastic wave is produced and transmitted through the bars and specimen. The elastic wave deforms the specimen plastically. It is important to know that the SHPB should not be applied to plastic wave propagation experiment. The SHPB can however be used to determine high strain rate characteristics of low impedance materials. With low-impedance materials, the incident bar-specimen interface moves almost freely under stress wave loading because most of the incident pulse is reflected back into the incident bar and a very small signal is transferred to the transmission bar. It is advisable to use of high-strength aluminum alloy for the incident bar and a hollow aluminum tube for the transmission bar. The hollow aluminum tube will cause an increase in σ_s according to Equation 44. Also, the hollow tube will produce an increased transmitted signal in the transmission bar. Another method of increasing the signal in the transmission bar when testing low-impedance material is by placing a circular piezoelectric transducer (an X-cut quartz crystal disk) embedded in the middle of an aluminum transmission bar of the same diameter to directly measure the time-resolved transmitted force. The X-cut quartz is much more sensitive in detecting forces in its x-direction than the indirect surface strain gage method. The mechanical impedance of the self-generating quartz transducer is also very close to the mechanical impedance of the aluminum transmission bar, which ensures that introduction of the quartz disk does not affect the one-dimensional wave propagation in the bar. In the current SHPB apparatus used in this experiment utilizes the aluminum bars both for incident and transmitted.

3.7.5 Samples Tested:

Seven plates of size 10.16 cm by 10.16 cm, were used to determine the physical characteristics. 1 inch diameter test samples were cut from these plates.

Table 8: Sample mass and fluid content for acoustic testing

Sample ID #	Sample makeup	Thickness (cm)	Mass of Dry sample (grams)	Mass of Wet Sample (grams)	% water by mass	Mass density (gm/cc)
1	Foam only	1.27	31.69			0.24
2	Open and 1 side 779 Kevlar	1.288	41.04			0.31
3	779 Kevlar both sides	1.392	46.25			0.34
4	Kevlar 2 x 3 both sides	1.356	47.79			0.33
5	779 Kevlar both sides	1.288	47.07	73.26	55.641	0.51
6	Kevlar 2 x 3 weave both sides	1.392	47.44	68.63	44.667	0.51
7	Aluminum					2.7

3.7.6 Observations

Figure 38 shows the response in both the incident and transmitted bars.

Figure 38: Typical Strain gage response plots

Test observations are provided in tables 9-15. To compare the observation of the FFC, an isotropic material i.e. Aluminum is considered. Table 15 gives the response of aluminum. Strain rate decreases with the stiffness of the material.

Table 9: Mechanical properties of foam sample (ID#1)

Stress σ_s (MPa)	Strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}_s$ (s ⁻¹)	Strain ϵ_s	Modulus (MPa)	Impact Vel. (m/s)
10.75393	537.6173	0.05395	199.3331	10.7
10.38436	495.2771	0.048235	215.2876	10.7
26.05064	1416.569	0.13312	195.6926	15.8
26.43303	1356.6	0.13597	194.4041	15.8
24.31467	1322.281	0.130893	185.7599	15.8
30.96925	1328.457	0.133597	231.8106	19.8
41.67875	1433.401	0.143285	290.8795	19.8

Table 10: Mechanical properties of foam + 1 side 779 Kevlar (ID#2)

Stress σ_s (MPa)	Strain ϵ_s	Strain Rate $\dot{\epsilon}_s$ (s ⁻¹)	Modulus (MPa)	Impact Vel. (m/s)
9.647455	0.101541	1014.973	95.01058	10.7
11.10345	0.10207	1032.915	108.7826	10.7
18.77432	0.113477	1140.833	165.4468	15.8
13.40576	0.119542	779.7041	112.1424	15.8
20.04733	0.18639	1839.758	107.5557	19.8
21.64255	0.157143	1562.798	137.7248	19.8

Table 11: Mechanical properties of foam + 779 Kevlar both sides (ID#3)

Stress σ_s (MPa)	Strain ϵ_s	Strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}_s$ (s ⁻¹)	Modulus (MPa)	Impact Vel. (m/s)
1.763975	0.064577	358.8964	27.31584	10.7
2.789896	0.034899	226.7614	79.94282	10.7
14.19881	0.084288	418.4153	168.4558	15.8
17.80375	0.086368	689.1492	206.1375	15.8
23.64478	0.099043	977.6156	238.733	19.8
33.61758	0.164117	1210.659	204.8393	19.8

Table 12: Mechanical properties of foam + 2x3 Kevlar both sides (ID#4)

Stress σ_s (MPa)	Strain ϵ_s	Strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}_s$ (s ⁻¹)	Modulus (MPa)	Impact Vel. (m/s)
0.467077	0.074601	445.1238	6.26102	10.7
0.369439	0.066333	375.4984	5.569474	10.7
0.636555	0.063994	364.8584	9.947137	10.7
0.738918	0.055115	549.2929	13.4068	15.8
0.936947	0.082989	571.6087	11.28997	15.8
1.255223	0.091433	922.5778	13.72838	19.8
1.404918	0.097226	959.3573	14.44997	19.8
1.67882	0.089524	917.7211	18.75279	19.8

Table 13: Mechanical properties of fluid-filled foam + 779 Kevlar both sides (ID#5)

Stress σ_s (MPa)	Strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}_s$ (s ⁻¹)	Strain ϵ_s	Modulus (MPa)	Impact Vel. (m/s)
1.598833	482.6347	0.05481	29.17072	10.7
1.961753	218.2006	0.040292	48.68851	10.7
2.675927	523.3456	0.076283	35.0789	10.7
2.700793	699.1439	0.070979	38.05033	15.8
3.025265	665.6543	0.084337	35.87118	15.8
3.719776	685.4099	0.09971	37.30601	15.8
8.801644	929.9557	0.094614	93.02682	19.8
7.566241	922.551	0.093318	81.08005	19.8

Table 14: Mechanical properties of fluid-filled foam + 2x3 Kevlar both sides (ID#6)

Stress σ_s (MPa)	Strain ϵ_s	Strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}_s$ (s ⁻¹)	Modulus (MPa)	Impact Vel. (m/s)
1.138536	0.031659	158.1064	35.96268	10.7
2.625775	0.056414	388.5866	46.5446	10.7
1.883701	0.050057	492.6979	37.63125	10.7
5.203985	0.083646	547.8092	62.21467	15.8

3.905243	0.059806	605.0019	65.29846	15.8
3.78235	0.070272	592.963	53.82449	15.8
6.869903	0.094839	951.5612	72.43789	19.8
9.740882	0.121893	797.3087	79.91326	19.8

Table 15: Mechanical properties of 6061-T6 Aluminum (ID#7)

Stress σ_s (MPa)	Strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}_s$ (s ⁻¹)	Strain ϵ_s	Modulus (MPa)	Impact Vel. (m/s)
50.03115	153.8843	0.013513	3702.338	10.7
52.58797	240.3437	0.024376	2157.371	10.7
51.07578	213.5514	0.02142	2384.488	10.7
58.99373	275.3403	0.027729	2127.486	15.8
62.90467	301.3191	0.030675	2050.664	15.8
61.49126	367.2329	0.036754	1673.037	15.8
72.52011	392.4277	0.039819	1821.255	19.8
77.15915	430.169	0.042889	1799.034	19.8
91.24592	355.8085	0.071723	1272.191	19.8

Figure 39: Variation of strain rate with impact velocity

For the same impact velocity, the strain rate (SR) in the material is different. The relation between these two parameters is given in the column 3 of table 8. The same relations are used to predict the strain rates caused by various impacts. Figure 39 gives the variation of strain rate with impact velocity.

Table 16: Strain Rate at extrapolated impact velocity

Sample ID #	Sample makeup	Relation between impact velocity (V) and strain rate (SR)	MK 46 Torpedo (average of 32-63 mph)	Space Shuttle Foam Debris (416 – 573 mph)	Boeing 737 (495 – 576 mph)	Micrometeo roids/Orbital Debris (4473 – 22,369 mph)
1	Foam only	SR= $-17.744 v^2 + 636.69 v - 4265$	426	-743009	-863573	-908169025
2	Open and 1 side 779 Kevlar	SR= $21.736v^2 - 588.5 v + 4833$	3128	951850	1103026	1113628055
3	779 Kevlar both sides	SR= $86.366 v - 685.91$	1137	18295	19869	514478
4	Kevlar 2 x 3 both sides	SR= $6.69 v^2 - 144.98 v + 1180.2$	1419	300602	347791	342972585
5	779 Kevlar both sides	SR= $56.788 v - 204.1$	995	12277	13311	338530

6	Kevlar 2 x 3 weave both sides	SR= 57.494 v- 286.66	927	12349	13397	342659
7	Aluminum	SR= 21.033 v- 21.604	422	4601	4984	125438

Figure 40a: Modulus versus strain rate

Figure 40b: Specific Modulus versus Strain rate

3.7.7. Discussion

Modifications were made to the conventional SHPB to investigate the impact response of a composite material consisting of polyurethane foam and Kevlar skins. A hollow aluminum tube was used for the output bar to produce a magnified signal of the transmitted pulse. The low impedance foam material causes most of the incident pulse to be reflected back into the incident bar and resulting in a very low transmitted signal through the specimen. An aluminum disc specimen was tested on the SHPB to verify that the low impedance material was responsible for most of the incident wave to be reflected back into the input bar. The results of the aluminum disc show that most of the incident pulse is transmitted through the sample and the same is registered in the output bar response. Table 15 shows the mechanical properties of the aluminum sample. The stress in the sample is a function of the transmitted pulse according to equation 44 and testing verifies that increased impact load on the aluminum sample produce greater stress since impact load intensity is directly measured on the input and output bars.

The aluminum sample reveals that as the strain rate or impact velocity is increased, modulus get decreased. The behavior is opposite in the case of composites, where the samples stiffened with the increase in the strain rate or impact velocity. The aluminum sample is initially a material with a higher modulus of elasticity and therefore will not experience as much a change in cross-section. Also, the material work-hardens as deformation proceeds, making it stiffer as strain

increases. This explains the increase in the modulus of the foam and composite specimens as the strain rate or impact velocity increases.

3.8 Thermal Management

Testing the thermal characteristics is a very important step in distinguishing what a composite material can and can't be used for as well as determining the adaptability of the material when exposed to high heat. The idea behind thermal management is that a material will "actively" cool itself if fluid is allowed to move within the solid structure. Since these tests are done on a composite with a fluid within a porous structure which is open cell polyurethane foam, the material itself will be able to adapt and change to different temperature environments.

If the composite material is heated in a particular area, then this will change the density of the fluid within that area. This heating will create conduction through the solid material as well as free convection due to the fluids changing buoyancy. The hot fluid will be more buoyant because of a lower density and viscosity and will be pushed up at the same time it transports heat to other areas and dissipates that heat. This action will actively cool the material at that location and manage the thermal shock being placed on the material by replacing the heated liquid with cooler liquid being pulled in from locations not in direct contact with the heat source.

It is known that vessels in the United States Navy, especially subs, need to be as quiet as possible but have many engineering problems to deal with in this sense. The many pumps and equipment needed to cool the reactors and other locations in the ship can cause a large amount of noise. It would be nice to reduce as much of these cooling systems that create unwanted noise as possible. It is known that Ohio class boomers and Seawolfs use the principle of natural circulation below 35% power on the engines. This is a feature that keeps these classes of submarines extremely quiet. Free convection is also used in the propulsion systems for Virginia class subs which is a General Electric Pressurized Water Nuclear Reactor S9G when over 50%. Natural circulation is the same thing as free convection in that a heating source will heat a fluid and changing buoyancy will make the hot fluid flow, thus pulling liquid that was not in contact with the heating source into its place. This cools the engines without using any machinery. The composite being tested here not only is highly acoustic dampening but works with heat through the principles of free convection to cool the material itself without ever needing to build a cooling system, even one that works on natural circulation.

3.8.1 ASTM Standards

A thorough investigation of possible test standards was carried out by looking into the various methods described by the American Society for Testing and Materials. This is a difficult process since what we wish to prove is a very unique problem. The goal of the test is to demonstrate that there is or is not an induced circulation within the structure of the composite. This unique problem had little to no match in any test offered by the ASTM standards [15-17].

3.8.1.1 ASTM E1225-04 : The Standard Test Method or Thermal Conductivity of Solids by means of the Guarded-Comparative-Longitudinal Heat Flow Technique did not meet the requirements of this project because the current composite is functionally graded and not a

homogeneous material. The results of this test would only offer the conductivity of a material and not the convection which is what the fluid will do demonstrate when heated.

3.8.1.2 ASTM E1530-06 : The Standard Test Method for Evaluating the Resistance to Thermal Transmission of Materials by the Guarded Heat Flow Meter Technique and fit some of the requirements because we would be able to find how well our material is resisting heat transfer but again only called for a homogenous material to be tested. The values that would result from this test would not be accurate since we are using a heterogeneous composite.

3.8.1.3 The ASTM Standard E 1952-06: Standard Test Method for Thermal Conductivity and Thermal Diffusivity by Modulated Temperature Differential Scanning Calorimetry has some good characteristics because it results in thermal conductivity which we could use, but in the end is also not a good fit for this project because we are dealing with a complex composite. This test is for homogenous non porous materials which is different than what we have because we are dealing with a open-cell porous composite (non-uniform).

Since there is no testing method for thermal management offered by ASTM standards one was created with experimental analysis and scientific thought in mind.

3.8.1.4 Initial Test

The design for these tests went through many iterations before a test apparatus was agreed upon and produced. The first thoughts were of making flat panels that can rest on top of a heating source such as a water bath. A simple testing method for the characterization of the composite was developed to demonstrate that in fact the heating of a certain location will create the circulation hypothesized due to changing viscosities. The test is constructed using a high heat clear Tygon hose loop wrapped around 3/4ths of the circumference of the loop with a Kevlar and epoxy composite and 4 thermocouples located as shown in figure . The water bath is placed in the specific location shown in figure 41 because this will allow the circulation to be very evident by the difference in temperatures at thermocouples 1 and 4.

Figure 41: Experimental apparatus and the four thermocouple locations

The vertical orientation of the hose loop would allow for testing of the hypothesis of free convection within the structure. The fluid flow is seen through the injection of dye through a syringe and needle once the material has undergone a period of heating. This initial testing can be used to test skin layer variables and characterize a temperature gradient around the material using the four thermocouples placed inside the hose.

Ultra-Clear Tygon PVC Tubing with $\frac{1}{2}$ " inner diameter and $\frac{3}{4}$ " outer diameter is cut to a length of 27". This length gives us a diameter of just over 8-1/2" which is needed to clear the oil bath. The Tygon tubing is then covered with the desired skin layer, in this case Kevlar, and care is taken to apply an even layer of the skin material so that no area may have a higher heat barrier than another. This means that all areas of the testing sample are uniform and no areas have extra skin layer material applied to them. A section of the hose loop which equates to $\frac{1}{4}$ of the circumference is left without the skin layer so that the fluid flow may be observed later in the testing. Once the Kevlar and epoxy has cured around the Tygon hose loop it is placed within the empty water bath.

Since the water bath must be attached to the side of the tubing a bath must be machined to specific dimensions so that the heating fluid will be sufficient to cover a length of the hose loop. The final aluminum machined bath has an inner diameter of 4" and a depth of 2- $\frac{3}{4}$ " for holding the liquid. A base is machined with a hole cut into it with an outer diameter of 1". This base is the location that the high heat hose loop is pushed through. The base is then sealed with Permatex Ultra Copper Maximum Temperature RTV Silicone Gasket Maker to prevent any leaks from developing at the location where the hose loop meets the base as well as where the bath walls meet the base as shown in figure 42.

Figure 42: High heat hose loop and sealed water bath

Once the Permatex gasket has fully cured the testing is ready to begin. The hose is filled with fluid and all air bubbles are allowed to escape through a small hole by injecting fluid with a needled syringe at a lower location. The hose is connected to make a complete ring using a barbed coupling fitting and small band clamps to allow for a watertight seal. The four thermocouples are pushed into their corresponding holes and 425ml of water is put into the water bath along with the immersion heater and a thermometer. The needled syringe takes on 1cc of dye and is positioned for later injection. Any small leaks, such as the point where the thermocouples are inserted, are sealed with polyethylene pressure tape so that no air is introduced into the hose.

The temperatures are taken through four NIST certified thermocouple thermometers with Type K thermocouple probes inside the hose loop as well as a Sixth Sense LT300 Infrared Thermometer for surface temperature measurements above and below the water bath. The water bath is monitored with a NIST certified ThermoFisher Scientific thermometer. The complete experimental apparatus is shown in figure 43.

Figure 43: Experiment being conducted on complete test set-up after dye injection

The thermocouples have a digital display showing both the temperature and elapsed time they have been on. This allows the thermocouples to be used as a temperature sensor as well as an accurate display of time the experiment has undergone. At the start, the temperatures are recorded and the immersion heater is powered on. The temperatures are then taken every 2 minutes for 10 minutes which is when the immersion heater is powered off and the dye is injected. Care must be taken when injecting the dye so as not to disturb the water within the hose.

After the 10 minute mark, temperature measurements are taken every 5 minutes for an additional 25 minutes for a total experiment time of 35 minutes. The time it takes the dye to complete one complete revolution is logged and this gives a time value for the circulation. There are 2 tests completed at this stage with 3 trials each, one with no Kevlar to act as a baseline and one with 1 layer of 779 plain correctional weave Kevlar.

3.8.1.5 Comprehensive Test

The comprehensive testing has the same type of experimental apparatus as the initial testing, but instead of having a hose loop there is a one piece foam structure. The oil bath had to be separated down the length of the walls and across the base as shown in figure 44, because this would allow for a single piece of foam to be used.

Figure 44: Split base and walls of water bath

The three types of samples tested at this stage were:

1. a dry foam core as a baseline,
2. a wet foam core, and
3. a wet foam core with 779 plain correctional weave Kevlar skin.

These were made by cutting the 1/2" thick super resilient polyurethane foam in a circular shape with an 8" inner diameter and 10" outer diameter giving a 1" thickness. This small 1" thickness makes it easier to replace the air within the open cells of the foam with fluid (water). For the 2 samples that have water in them they are sealed with DAP Dynaflex 230 Premium Clear Sealant which keeps the water within the foam core and is shown in figure 5.

Figure 45: The wet core sample after sealant application and

partially cured (noticed some sealant is still white and uncured)

The next step for the 3rd sample which has a wet core and Kevlar skin layer is to cut the Kevlar to size and epoxy the Kevlar to the wet core. The Kevlar is cut with Kevlar cutting shears and combined with MAS Low Viscosity Epoxy Resin and MAS Slow Hardener. Once this has cured the sample is sealed into the water bath and sealed with Permatex Ultra Copper Maximum Temperature RTV Silicone Gasket Maker as was done in the initial testing and is shown in figure 46.

Figure 46: Sample 3 sealed into the water bath

The testing procedure for the comprehensive testing is different from the initial testing because these tests are done with a heating source at steady state. The test begins with the sample in the water bath at room temperature and thermocouple measurements are taken. The immersion heater is then turned on. In about 10 minutes the water bath reaches a temperature of 150°F and is kept there for 25 minutes. Temperature measurements are taken from the 4 thermocouple locations as well as the water bath temperature and surface temperatures 1" above the water line and 1" below the water line every 5 minutes. At the 35 minute mark (by this time the temperatures in the sample have ample time to reach steady state) the heating source is increased to 180°F and kept at steady state until the 50 minute mark. This allows for the materials thermal management characteristics to be observed at two different points in one test.

3.8.2 Observations

3.8.2.1 Initial Test

The initial tests were set up with the thermocouple locations shown in figure 41 and show the natural convection process taking place within the hose loops of each sample and all trials. The flow in all trials was clockwise showing the heat rising and circulating through the loop. The baseline trials represent the high Tygon hose loop with no skin layer while the 779C trials represent the Tygon hose loop with a 779 correctional plain weave Kevlar skin layer. A typical table of the values recorded is shown in table 17.

Table 17 – Thermal Management of baseline sample (No Kevlar) Trial 1

Temp Sensor	Start	2min	4min	6min	8min	10min	15min	20min	25min	30min	35min	Max Temps
1	70.2	72	75.7	79.2	82.8	88.5	94.8	97.9	98.6	98.2	97.2	99.3
2	70.2	70.2	71.6	71.4	73	76.1	80.8	83.3	84.4	84.4	84.2	85.1
3	67.6	67.3	67.6	67.6	68	70.5	71.6	73.8	74.8	75.4	75.2	75.6
4	67.8	67.5	67.6	67.5	67.5	68.4	68.9	69.4	70	70.3	70.3	70.9
Water Bath	68	90	98	120	134	149	142	135	129	122	119	149
Above Bath	67.4	66.2	66.9	66.5	69	70.3	68	67.6	66.5	66.3	67.8	70.3
Below Bath	67.8	73.1	79.4	88.3	96.6	105	104.1	102.1	99.4	95.4	93.6	105

Trial	Time (min)
1	15
2	17
3	16

Figures 47 (a-c): Baseline tests of Initial Test Method

Figures 48 (a-c): 779 plain weave Kevlar tests of Initial Test Method

3.8.2.2 Comprehensive Testing

The thermocouples for the comprehensive testing were set up in the same manner as in the initial testing and shown in figure 49. The weight of the foam samples in tables 20 and 21 are different because the wet core sample was remade using a slightly smaller diameter to get a better fluid intake as it was found to be somewhat less than what was possible. The graphs on the left are of the water bath at steady state at 150°F while the ones on the right are that of steady state at 180°F which was done between the 35 and 45 minute mark.

Figure 49: The locations of the four thermocouples during the comprehensive tests

Figures 50 (a-c): Dry core layer tests of Comprehensive Test Method

Figures 51(a-c): FF core layer tests of Comprehensive Test Method

Table 20 –Fluid Absorption for Wet Core Sample	
Sample Completion	Weight (g)
Foam Only	62.64
Foam with Water	170.27
Foam with Water and Silicone	134.13

Figures 52 (a-c): Complete 779 plain weave Kevlar tests of Comprehensive Test Method

Table 21 – Fluid Absorption for FFC Sample	
Sample Completion	Weight (g)
Foam Only	113.57
Foam with Water	186.67
Foam with Water and Silicone	195.54
Completed with Kevlar Skin	

3.8.3 Discussion

3.8.3.1 Initial Tests

The tests done in the initial testing phase showed much promise in the idea of free convection within a solid structure. This is shown because thermocouple 1 is 1" above the water bath and thermocouple 4 is 1" below the water bath. This has definitely been shown in the initial tests as one can see thermocouple 1 is much hotter than thermocouple 4. At some points there is over 30°F difference between thermocouples 1 and 4 although they are both only 1" from the hot water and this is only due to their difference in location, 1 being above the location of heating and 4 being below the location of heating.

The graphs in figure 47 and 48 show that in all trials the heat is being dissipated as it travels through the material. Thermocouple 2 is a lower temperature than thermocouple 1, thermocouple 3 is lower than 2, and 4 is lower than 3. It is also shown that by the time the water has reached thermocouple 4 it is nearly back to its original temperature. Thermocouple 4's largest increase in temperature happened during baseline trial 2 with a temperature change of 6.8°F and is shown in figure 47.2. This increase happened over a span of 35 minutes of heating. The fluid is being cooled by transferring to the outside material and from mixing with cooler fluid that is far from the heating source.

The flow is shown to be clockwise through the injection of dye at the location directly opposite the water bath. The clockwise flow is expected since this would result from the buoyancy forces rising up from the heat source and pushing the flow through the hose loop. The dye injection can be seen in figure 53.

3.8.3.2 Comprehensive Test

The comprehensive tests also show the induced circulation within the material due to the heating source in one area of the material. Free convection must be taking place because thermocouple 4 is nearly unaffected by the heat while thermocouple 1 sees temperature increases. The only heat transfer that is heating thermocouple 4 is conduction through the foam and can't be the fluid because the fluid is being pushed up through the material.

It can also be seen through the comprehensive tests that by the time any fluid reaches thermocouple 2 the heat has already been dissipated. The only thermocouple sensor that sees large increases in temperature is thermocouple 1 and this is because of the close location to the heating source. These tests are also being conducted at 150°F and thermocouple 1 never sees over 80.8°F for either of the tests with wet core layers and never over 86.2°F for the dry core layer.

The dry core layer tests show a large initial spike in temperature due to the air being inside the open celled structure being able to quickly move through the material. The air can much more freely flow than the water that is used in the 2 other comprehensive tests and therefore is much more unpredictable the way it acts and it also takes less time to heat up due to water's high specific weight.

As one can see in the figure 52 trials, the heating of the core takes much longer than the other 2 comprehensive tests. This is because of the increase in material and larger thermal mass. The heating source is a water bath so the heat must travel through the material to affect the core where the thermocouples are registering the temperatures. In this case the heat must travel through the epoxy covered Kevlar skin layer, and then through the foam, which in turn heats the fluid and travels up through the open cells of the material. This is seen through the much more gradual growth to the highest temperature as seen in the figure 52 trials as compared to the sharp increase attainment of steady state as seen in the figure 50 and figure 51 trials.

It is also evident that the dry core layer released the heat after reaching the 180°F steady state mark while the other 2 fluid filled samples held the heat for longer. This is again due to the larger thermal mass.

3.9 Overall Conclusions

A fluid filled “Engineered Layer” comprising a core layer of cellular foam plus skin layer/s is developed and characterized under acoustics. Sound transmission loss at low frequency (250 – 1000 Hz) and high frequency (1-10 kHz) were obtained. Limited tests were performed to determine its underwater characteristics. To characterize its explosive behavior, impact tests at moderate velocity were performed using Split Hopkinson Pressure bar. Thermal management of the material is investigated using a new and innovative method created with experimental analysis and scientific thought in mind. Major conclusions are:

1. **Thermal management** tests demonstrated that there is induced circulation due to convection within the material due to the heating source in one area of the material.
2. The dry core layer tests show a large initial spike in temperature due to the presence of air in the interstitial pores which can quickly move through the material. Dry core layer released the heat after reaching the 180°F steady state mark while the other 2 fluid filled samples held the heat for a longer duration. This is again due to their larger thermal mass.

3. Within the frequency range of 250-1000 Hz the core layer was found to have 25% higher **acoustic** transmission loss (TL) than that predicted by the acoustic mass law. Under high frequency, the transmission loss (TL) through a $\sim \frac{1}{2}$ inch thick sample of the composite is found to be as high as 132dB. Influence of fluid in the pores was found to be around 36 dB, which is equivalent to a layer of 5" thick building wall with 2"x 4" wood stud framing covered by 2 sheets of gypsum board on both sides.
4. Under impact load, the aluminum sample reveals that as the strain rate or impact velocity is increased, modulus gets decreased. The behavior is opposite in the case of the developed fluid filled composites, where the samples stiffened with the increase in the strain rate. Under high strain rate during an explosion, the material is also found to develop stiffness quickly but temporarily. This can be viewed as "**adaptive nature**" of the developed material.

3.10 References

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Appendix A: Skin Layer Stress-Strain Test Results

Kevlar 3x2 Twill 1-Ply

Material	E ₁ psi	E ₂ psi	v ₁	v ₂	G ₁₂ psi
Kevlar 3x2 Twill Weave (1-ply)	4842213	7377712	0.094744	0.120626	356243

Failed Samples

Kevlar 3x2 Twill 2-Ply

Material	E1	E2	v1	v2	G12
Kevlar 3x2 Twill Weave (2-ply)	psi	psi			psi
	10212745	7754836	0.054614	0.328872	708780

Kevlar 2x2 Twill 1-Ply

Material	E1	E2	v1	v2	G12
Kevlar 2x2 Plain Weave (1-ply)	psi	psi			psi
	6604791	7061773	0.271383	0.259412	359850

Kevlar 779 Correctional Weave 1-Ply

Material	E1	E2	v1	v2	G12
Kevlar 779 Correctional (1-ply)	psi	psi			psi
	1512327	6744015	0.15938	0.24501	520622

Carbon Fiber 2x2 Plain Weave (1-ply)

Material	E1	E2	v1	v2	G12
Carbon Fiber 2x2 Plain Weave (1-ply)	psi	psi			psi
	10131991	10197570	0.060619	0.225771	792098

